

Developing Continuous Signal-Based Neutron Noise Methods by Experiments and Simulations

Máté Szieberth^{1,*}, Máté István Boros¹, Gergely Klujber¹, Imre Pázsit²

¹Institute of Nuclear Techniques, Budapest University of Technology and Economics (BME), H-1111 Budapest, Hungary;

²Division of Subatomic, High Energy and Plasma Physics, Department of Physics, Chalmers University of Technology, SE-412 96 Göteborg, Sweden

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ABSTRACT

Neutron noise methods are used in reactor physics to measure reactivity and other kinetic parameters of a system by analyzing neutron counting statistics. A stochastic model of the signal from fission chambers has been developed in recent years, showing that the quantities sought in neutron noise measurements can also be reconstructed from a continuous signal, thereby excluding the dead-time effect of overlapping detector pulses. The paper addresses the underlying theory and presents simulations and experimental results to prove the correctness of the theory and the practical applicability of the new method.

Keywords: neutron noise, Rossi-alpha, autocorrelation, Feynman-alpha, variance-to-mean

1. INTRODUCTION

Neutron noise techniques are well-established methods for measuring the reactivity of subcritical and critical quasi-zero-power systems since the dawn of nuclear power. In higher neutron flux environments, however, the increased count rate results in detector-pulse pile-up. This introduces a dead-time effect, leading to lost counts and worse measurement statistics, and eventually rendering the traditional pulse-based counting unusable. The proposed solution to this issue is to use the raw continuous voltage signal from the fission chamber detectors. This approach is inherently resistant to dead-time effects and therefore allows application at higher reactor power. Using neutron detectors in the current mode to estimate reactor kinetic parameters via neutron noise measurements has previously been investigated by others, with promising results [1, 2]. The main difference in our approach is the use of higher sampling rates to resolve the detector pulse shape, enabling advanced signal processing and allowing the measurement of higher α values relevant to higher-order kinetic modes and fast systems. We have also conducted detailed investigations into the measurement conditions under which the method based on the continuous detector signal is feasible and provides an advantage over pulsed-based methods.

2. THEORY

A simple theory of continuous signals of fission chambers, which provides an elegant derivation of the classic Campbell theorems for uncorrelated detection events was elaborated by L. Pál [3]. In the formalism, the detector pulse shape was written as the product of a deterministic shape $f(t)$ and a random amplitude η with probability distribution $w(\eta)$. In this way, the probability density function of the pulse value u at time t is written as

$$h(u, t) = \int_0^{\infty} \delta[u - \eta f(t)] w(\eta) d\eta. \quad (1)$$

*szieberth@reak.bme.hu

The formalism was thereafter extended for correlated detection events from a fission chain [4], which is true for multiplying systems and is the essence of noise techniques.

With these assumptions, the auto-covariance (ACF) and variance-to-mean ratio (VTM) functions were derived for the continuous signal, which asymptotically matched the well-established Rossi- α and Feynman- α formulas known for discrete, pulse-based signals. However, the ACF includes an additional exponential term with the detector pulse decay constant (α_e), which also distorts the VTM function. Luckily, in most cases, the fundamental prompt decay constant of the multiplying system (α) is by

Figure 1. The ACF of the continuous signal for different detector pulse speeds, and the VTM for different levels of subcriticality.[4]

several orders of magnitude slower than the decay constant of the detector pulse, meaning that these distortion effects are significant only in a very short initial section of the relevant region of these functions, and these short sections can simply be ignored without significantly impacting the accuracy of the evaluation. However, when determining higher-order α -modes of the system, α_e and the sought α value can become more comparable, which can lead to problems.

As the simulation results presented in the following section show, the distortion of the detector pulse shape can be mitigated when using pairs of detectors and computing the cross-covariance (CCF) and the cross-covariance-to-mean ratio (CTM) functions of the two signals.

Another possible way to mitigate the problem caused by the detector's finite time constant is to deconvolve the average pulse shape from the signal. If the assumption in eq. (1) holds, then the continuous signal is the convolution of the average pulse shape and Dirac delta pulses:

$$c(t) = \sum_{n=1}^N \eta_n f(t - t_n) = \sum_{n=1}^N \eta_n \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(t') \delta(t - t_n - t') dt' = \sum_{n=1}^N \eta_n [f * \delta](t - t_n) \quad (2)$$

Here, there are N detected neutrons during the measurement period, t_n is the time of the detection of the n th neutron, and η_n is the amplitude of the corresponding detector pulse. The average pulse shape $f(t)$ can easily be measured; therefore, it can be assumed to be known. In that case, we can deconvolve it from the recorded continuous signal, which can be performed in the Fourier space:

$$\mathcal{F}^{-1} \left\{ \frac{\mathcal{F}\{c\}}{\mathcal{F}\{f\}} \right\} = \sum_{n=1}^N \eta_n \cdot \delta(t - t_n) \quad (3)$$

This, without the η_n random amplitudes, would be the ideal form of the continuous signal, as we would ideally get an infinitely short pulse at each neutron detection. The integral of this ideal continuous function would simply be the counting function of the neutron detection events.

3. SIMULATIONS

To determine and compare the usability domains of both traditional pulse-based and continuous signals, simulations of measurement data were performed. The simulations were performed using a simple program that implements a 1-speed point Monte Carlo model of a subcritical multiplying system with an external source.

First, a *reference signal* was created, which is the time-stamped data of detections from the Monte Carlo point reactor model with one delayed neutron group. This was converted to the *continuous signal* by adding an average pulse shape and random amplitude variation. Finally, a time-stamped *pulsed signal* was produced from the continuous signal with simulated data processing by specifying a discrimination threshold level and non-extendable deadtime.

Results of the different signal types were compared while increasing the detection rate through the intensity of the external source, and while increasing the α theoretical prompt decay constant. The α value was changed by increasing all the λ_x intensities of all the reaction types. This can be regarded as changing the speed of the neutrons, i.e. the neutron spectrum.

3.1. The simulation of detector signals

First, the times of each neutron detection event (a fission reaction in the fission chamber detector) were produced by the Monte Carlo simulation. Then, using $f(t)$ average pulse shapes taken from earlier measurements [5] with KNT-31 fission chambers at Training Reactor of the Budapest University of Technology and Economics (BME TR)[6] and $w(\eta)$ amplitude (maximum voltage value) distributions, the continuous voltage signal of the detector was produced with some additive Gaussian noise component. Finally, the pulse-based signal was generated from the continuous signal using an appropriately chosen threshold level. The fission intensity λ_f was obtained from the MCNP[7] model of the BME TR. The model yielded a generation time of $\Lambda \approx 6.9 \cdot 10^{-5}$ s, from which the fission intensity is $\lambda_f = \frac{1}{\Lambda \cdot \bar{\nu}} \approx 5870$ s⁻¹. Delayed neutrons (precursors) were omitted from the simulations. This way, the simulated system at steady-state acts as a critical system, the constant-intensity external source replacing the role of the delayed neutron precursors at equilibrium population.

3.2. Increasing the detection intensity

One of the main goals of this research is to demonstrate the usability of the continuous signal for higher detection rates compared to the traditional pulse-based signal. In the simulations, the detection rate was varied by changing the intensity of the external Poissonian source in the subcritical system. This source intensity was changed between $5 \cdot 10^6$ s⁻¹ and $2 \cdot 10^8$ s⁻¹ while keeping all the other system parameters constant, resulting in a theoretical α value of 107.2 s⁻¹. Higher source intensities have not been tested because the computation time required for both the Monte Carlo simulation and the evaluation of the pulse-based and reference signals became too long. The ratio between the detected neutrons per detector and the source neutrons was approximately $\lambda_d/\alpha \approx 0.01$ detected neutron/source neutron.

For all signal types, the 2-detector variants of the Rossi- α and Feynman- α methods were used, resulting in a best-case scenario for both continuous and pulse-based signals. Figure 2 shows the results of all 3 signal types of a simulation with $5 \cdot 10^7$ s⁻¹ source intensity (approximately $5 \cdot 10^5$ s⁻¹ neutron/s/detector) At this level of source intensity, the traditional pulse-based signal is on the edge of usability, as only the cross-covariance-to-mean function can be fitted successfully to the theoretical Feynman- α function, with much higher uncertainties than for the reference and continuous signals.

The results obtained from all the simulations with source intensities ranging from $5 \cdot 10^6$ s⁻¹ and $2 \cdot 10^8$ s⁻¹ are shown in Figure 3. It shows that, all the way to the maximum source intensity, the con-

Figure 2. Rossi- α (cross-covariance, top) and Feynman- α (cross-covariance-to-mean, bottom) results obtained from the Reference signal (left), the Pulse-based signal (middle) and the Continuous signal (right) based on a simulation with $5 \cdot 10^7 \text{ s}^{-1}$ source intensity.

Figure 3. Rossi- α (cross-covariance, left) and Feynman- α (cross-covariance-to-mean, right) results obtained from the Reference signal, the Pulse-based signal and the Continuous signal.

tinuous signal provides a good estimate of the α value, similar to the reference signal, whereas the pulse-based signal becomes increasingly unusable at higher intensities.

3.3. Increasing the α value of the system

The second parameter changed in the simulations was the system's prompt decay constant, α , up to 10^5 s^{-1} . Higher α values are relevant when one tries to estimate the decay constant corresponding to higher-order kinetic modes of the system. Accurate measurement of higher-order α modes is well known to be challenging with traditional pulse-based signals.

The simulations were tuned to yield an average detection rate of 10^5 neutrons/s/detector. This is an intensity for which the traditional pulse-based signal gave satisfactory results with $\alpha \approx 107.2 \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Alongside the pulse-based and continuous signals, the possible benefits of deconvolving the average pulse shape from the continuous signal were also investigated. Namely, after deconvolving the continuous signal, the resulting deconvolved continuous signal was transformed into a pulse-based signal, similar to how the traditional pulse-based signal is produced from the original continuous signal, using an appropriate threshold level.

First, the sensitivity of the proposed inverse Fourier deconvolution technique with regard to additive white noise was investigated. As expected, the results show that this simple deconvolution technique is

quite sensitive to electronic noise. However, as long as the NSR remains well under 1%, even an inverse Fourier deconvolution gives satisfactory results. The application of more sophisticated deconvolution techniques, such as the Richardson-Lucy or Wiener deconvolution, largely improves the tolerance to noise. More detailed results of comparing the inverse Fourier and Wiener deconvolutions with various amounts of additive noise will be presented in [8].

The results of all the simulations with α values ranging from 1250 s^{-1} to 10^5 s^{-1} are collected in Figure 4. With the continuous and traditional pulse-based signals, the theoretical Rossi- α and Feynman- α

Figure 4. Rossi- α (left) and Feynman- α (right) evaluations of different signal types with different theoretical α values. For the continuous and (traditional) pulse-based signals, the charts contain the results obtained from using a single detector (ACF, VTM) and detector pairs (CCF, CTM).

functions could not be fitted successfully for larger α values. These results are missing from Figure 4. One can see that using *detector pairs* instead of a *single detector* benefits the traditional pulse-based signal, but especially the continuous signal in terms of evaluability and/or uncertainty of the estimation. The continuous signal is a clear improvement over the traditional pulse-based signal, whether using a single detector or a pair. However, it systematically underestimates the α value over 20000 s^{-1} when using detector pairs. The reason for this will need to be investigated further. The deconvolved pulse-based signal using a *single detector* generally gives as (or even more) accurate results as the continuous signal using *detector pairs*.

4. EXPERIMENTAL

Experiments were also conducted to demonstrate the feasibility and advantages of using the continuous signal and deconvolving the average pulse shape in neutron noise measurements. In this paper, some selected results from two different sets of measurements conducted at the Kyoto University Critical Assembly (KUCA) and BME TR are presented, while they are planned to be published in full detail in a journal paper soon [8].

4.1. Measurements at KUCA

The set of measurements presented in this section was performed in 2019, and the results were published in conference paper [9]. The reader is referred to that paper for a more detailed description. Recently, with the use of the new pulse-shape deconvolution technique and other developments, additional measurements could be successfully evaluated, as presented here.

As described in [9], the measurements were performed in several subcritical and a critical KUCA core configurations. In critical condition, measurements were performed at three different power levels, including one at which the count rate was sufficiently low that pulse overlap was negligible and no dead-time problem existed for the pulse-counting method. Due to the low count rate, the measurements at that power level could be evaluated both with the pulse counting and based on the continuous signal, for comparison. Measurements were also performed at elevated power levels to prove the applicability

of the new methodology.

Some earlier and new results for the fitted α -value obtained with different evaluation methods in critical condition at the lowest and one elevated power level are shown in Table I. One should note that the uncertainties of the fitted parameters reported here were obtained without accounting for the variances and covariances of the data points, which may lead to a significant underestimation of the fitting error. It was shown in [10], where a correct method for uncertainty estimation is also given, which has not yet been applied to the present evaluations. Therefore, the scattering of the results is considered to be largely due to statistical uncertainty. Furthermore, no reference α -value is available for the unique core configuration used, which also limits the conclusions from the measurements. Previously, only the results of Rossi- α evaluations at the lowest power level were published, showing good agreement with the counts-based evaluation, which proves the unbiasedness of the method. On the other hand, the Feynman- α evaluations and all evaluations of the elevated power level measurements showed a serious bias of unknown origin. Recently, in-depth investigations attributed this bias to the frequency transfer behavior of the data acquisition electronics, particularly the preamplifier, which introduces negative correlations. Better understanding of the reasons behind the effect made possible the fitting of a proper Feynmann- α -value at least at the lower power level, which can be seen in Fig. 5. One can observe the local maximum around 10^{-4} s, beyond which a valley is produced by the negative correlations in the signal. At the higher power level, the continuous signal-based evaluations are not possible for this data set due to the extent of the bias. This emphasizes that continuous signal-based noise methods require specialized data-acquisition electronics with linear frequency transfer behaviour, which aligns with current development. On the other hand, the deconvolution method was also applied to this data set, producing good results even at the elevated power level, both with the Feynmann- and Rossi- α evaluations.

Table I. Fitted α -values [1/s] obtained from KUCA measurement at two power levels and by different evaluation methods.

Power [mW]	Detector	continuous		pulsed		deconvolution	
		Rossi	Feynman	Rossi	Feynman	Rossi	Feynman
18.4	A	-	-	-	-	238.7 ± 2.3	229.7 ± 0.8
1.84	A	274.4 ± 1.1	231 ± 1.1	241.6 ± 2.1	243 ± 2.1	227.7 ± 11.8	222.3 ± 0.8
	D	272.1 ± 1.1	229.6 ± 4.9	238.2 ± 2.8	244.3 ± 7.3	237.1 ± 10.7	237.7 ± 1.2

Figure 5. Evaluation of a measurement performed in KUCA, a) with the pulse counting method (on the left) and b) with the method based on continuous signals (on the right). Beyond the prompt decay constant α one delayed neutron time constant α_d was also fitted. The red parts of the curves were excluded from the fit since they deviate from the theoretical curve due to the a) dead time and b) negative correlations as described in the text. [8, 9]

4.2. Measurements at BME TR

More recently, in April 2024, a set of measurements was also conducted at the Training Reactor of the Budapest University of Technology and Economics (BME TR). BME TR is a light water moderated and cooled reactor of 100 kW maximum thermal power. The core consists of EK-10 type fuel assemblies, containing 10% enriched UO_2 in a magnesium metallic matrix. The fuel region is surrounded by graphite reflector assemblies.

For the measurements, a KNT-31-type fission chamber was placed in a vertical dry channel of the Training Reactor. The center of the dry channel is approximately 40 cm away from the reactor core. This resulted in a detection efficiency that was significantly lower than that used in the simulations.

Preliminary results are presented in Tab. II for measurements performed under critical conditions at power levels ranging from 0.1 W to 10 W, resulting in count rates of 5,000 to 500,000 counts per second (cps), respectively. The estimated critical α of the reactor is about 120 s^{-1} . One can observe that the fitted α -values vary in wide range with considerably high standard deviation. The overall weak statistics of these measurements can be attributed to the low detection efficiency achieved by the detector position being well outside the reactor core. Furthermore, Monte Carlo simulations showed that the secondary neutrons emitted from the fission chamber at detection, scatter back from the surrounding materials and produce a correlated detection with a time constant of about 1500 s^{-1} . Due to the low efficiency, this effect can introduce a serious bias, especially at higher power levels, which explains that the results of the fits are scattered between this and the actual prompt decay constant ($\sim 120\text{ s}^{-1}$) of the reactor. In one case, the fitting of both time constants was also possible. In conclusion, the measurement conditions did not allow the accurate measurement of the prompt decay constant in most configurations. However, the results show that the continuous signal and the deconvolution based methods both are applicable on orders of magnitudes higher count rates than the pulse counting, which could be evaluated only at the lowest power level.

Table II. Fitted α -values [1/s] obtained from BME TR measurements at three power levels and by different evaluation methods.

Power [W]	pulsed		continuous		deconvolution	
	Rossi	Feynman	Rossi	Feynman	Rossi	Feynman
0.1	254.7 ± 196	219 ± 90	138.7 ± 20^a	-	1177 ± 249	121 ± 31
1.0	-	-	1260 ± 52	-	174.8 ± 188	163.1 ± 41
10.0	-	-	1314 ± 57	-	1930 ± 710	296 ± 320

^a Dual exponential fit was used and a higher α of 1490 ± 141 was also found.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The paper presented the methodology of neutron noise evaluation for continuous detector signals, developed based on the stochastic model of the signal. Simulations showed that the new method is more tolerant of high count rates than the traditional pulse counting methods. Proof-of-concept experiments were performed to demonstrate the applicability of neutron noise measurements based on continuous detector signals with the help of a data acquisition system developed for this purpose. A new methodology based on the deconvolution of the contribution of the pulse shape from the continuous signals has been developed and successfully applied in the experiments. Electronic noise and non-linearities in the electronics pose challenges for the continuous signal-based measurements; therefore, the most important line of further development concerns the data acquisition chain. A high-end data acquisition tool has been purchased to overcome the limitations of the present one and further develop the new

methodologies toward practical applications. In order to test these improvements, the continuation of the measurement campaign at the BME Training Reactor is planned.

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